

URBANIZATION PROCESS IN KHOREZM DURING THE ARAB OCCUPATION

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Abstract: A number of historical and archaeological material evidences dating back to the 10th century prove that Khorezm experienced rapid economic growth. This progressive process was reflected in the booming growth of cities in Khorezm. This article is about the occupation of Arabs to Khorezm and its urbanization during this occupations.

Key words: Historical material, urbanization, process, rapid economic, evidence, Arabs

Arab historian Tabari showed that when the Arabs conquered Khorezm, there were only 3 cities - Kat (Fir), Hazorasp and Urganch. Another Arab historian, Al-Istahri, enumerated the cities of Khorezm around 930-933: Khorezm (Kas), Dargan, Hazorasp, Khiva, Khushmisan, Ardakhushmisan, Safardiz, Nuzbar, Kardaronkhos, Kardar, Barategin, Mazminiya, Jurjaniya (mentions thirteen names such as Gurganj). Finally, the Arab author al-Maqdisi, who came to Khorezm in 985, writes that the number of oasis cities was 32. In particular, it is Kas, Gardman, Aykhan, Arzakhiva, Nukfag, Kardar, Mizdahkhan, Jashira, Sadvar, Zardukh, Barategin, Madkaminiya on the right bank of Amudarya; located on the left bank of Jurjonia (Gurganj), Nuzvar, Zamakhshar, Ruzund, Vazarmand, Vaskahankas, Rakhushmisan, Madamisan, Khiva, Kardaronhos, Hazorasp, Jigarband, Jaz, Dargan, Jit, Little Jurjonia, the second Jit, Sadvar, He showed that there are cities such as Masasan, Kardar, Andarstan. In addition, it is noted that on the roads to Khorezm there were settlements such as Shorakhan, Khas, Nuzkat, Darsan, Juvikan, Amir, Barabsar, Vardara.

The appearance of cities in Khorezm is connected with the development of agriculture and handicrafts, especially the expansion of artificial irrigation gave it a strong impetus. "Starting from Hazorasp, canals were dug on the banks of Jayhun," wrote al-Istahri. "Among them is the Hazorasp canal, which is half the length of the Gawhara canal. Then, at a distance of two farsahs from Hazorasp, there is the Kardaronhos canal, which is larger than the canal. After it comes the canal of Khiva, and it is larger than Kardaronchos, and ships travel from it to Khiva." So, according to Istakhri, on the left bank of the Amudarya, Hazorasp (Hassa Canal), Kardaronkhos (Kal'ajiq, Davud Qala Canal), Khiva (Polvanyop), Madra (Gazavot), Buva (Yormish) and Vadaq (later Shahabad)

) channels. The ends of the Buva and Vadaq canals were connected and brought to Jurjania (Gurganj). Many of these canals were used by ships, and they played the role of a special artery in internal trade.

The growth of cities is one of the important aspects of the overall economic development of the country, and it indicates the strengthening and expansion of the economic relations of the Khorezm urban civilization with the surrounding steppes and distant countries. Khorezm merchants, as in ancient times, with steppe nomads in the place of Turkmenistan and Western Kazakhstan, along the Volga - Khazaria (later Dashti Kipchak) and Bulgaria, and finally with the vast Slavs of Eastern Europe strengthened trade relations with the world. As early as the 10th century, Istahri wrote about the expansion of trade relations with the above regions and about the people of Khorezm in general: "Khorazm is a fertile city (medina) with a lot of food and fruits, but there are no nuts; "Here many things are made of cotton and wool, and these things are transported to far and wide places. The distinguishing feature of the inhabitants is their wealth and their tendency to show bravery." The author of "Hudud al-Alam" written at the end of the 10th century writes the following about the city of Kat: "The wealth of the city is great. From here, pillow covers, folk clothing, thread gauze, felt, black house, rukhbin (a type of cheese) are produced.) is released".

Among the goods brought from Bulgaria, Al-Maqdisi also mentioned the products produced in Khorezm: "Khorezm has a lot of grapes, raisins, almond kernels, sesame, striped clothes. , carpets, blankets, wonderful kimhob, bedclothes called "mulkham", locks, colorful clothes, bows that only the strongest people can have, a special kind of cheese, whey, fish are made. Ships are made there, and even when they are made, they are finished." In the list provided by Al-Maqdisi, we can see that among the goods exported from Khorezm, there were also products of metalworking (lock), weaponry (bow), and shipbuilding industry. As the types of Khorezm craft industry products exported from the country have increased year by year, their marketability has also increased.

The famous Arab traveler Yaqut al-Hamawi, who was in Khorezm on the eve of the Mongol-Tatar invasion, wrote in his work "Mu'jam al-buldan" ("Dictionary of Countries"): "I went there in 616 (1219-1220) I went there. I have never seen such a crowded and green country. The crops are well cared for, the villages are lined up close to each other, there are many separate courtyards and pastures. Even in the steppe There are many forts. It is difficult to find an

unmaintained, uninhabited place in the rustics (farming districts) of the country. There are many green groves, especially the gujumu mulberry, because they (the population) need timber for construction, and the mulberry leaf for silkworms. It doesn't matter whether you walk in all its provinces or in its markets (in terms of population size). No place in the world is as prosperous as Khorezm. A must not be a densely populated country. Most of Khorezm's population addresses are cities with plenty of markets and life necessities. A village without a market is rare. All this is happening in general security and peace.

Eastern features were fully embodied in the cities that existed in Khorezm on the eve of the Mongol invasion and after it. According to the medieval Persian historian Zakariya ibn Muhammad al-Qazvini: "There was another small city in the middle of each city. The middle of the small city was called kohandiz. They called Sugrah (small city). It was surrounded by a wall and had several gates. Around Shahrstan was a large city called Madinat ul-Kubra, which was also surrounded by a wall and had several gates. In the suburbs of big cities there were vineyards and orchards, and around them - cultivated fields.

Life is bubbling in the cities of Khorezm, trade and crafts are highly developed. A variety of handicrafts, jewelry, clothing, carpets, leather, wool, oil, soap, weapons, saddlery, fruit, dried fruit, silks, jewelry, made by artisans. and many other products were sold both in the domestic market and in the foreign market. Yakut Hamavi, who was in the city in 1219, said: "I have not seen such a great, rich and beautiful city as Gurganj." Speaking about Gurganj, Zakariyo Qazvini said: "It is a very large city on the banks of the Jayhun River and has a large population. He was guarded by angels like a city in heaven and a bride in a garden." Historical sources have preserved a lot of information about other trading cities of Khorezm. Ibn Fadlan, an Arab diplomat who was in Khorezm in 922, said: "Ardakhushmisan is a big city with crowded markets and a prosperous population. Ardakhushmisan is located between Kat and Gurganj and is a city on the banks of Amudarya, which can be reached by waterway. In the work "Hudud al-Olam" it is stated that "Ardakhushmi is the gathering place of merchants". Yagut Hamavi, who was in Ardakhushmisan in 1219, equates the city with Nisibin, one of the largest cities in Syria. But the tourist said that the city of Ardakhushmisan is more magnificent, has more goods in the markets, more inhabitants and wealthier.

The city of Urganch, which was restored during the Golden Horde, gained importance again as the main center connecting Volgaboyi, Dashti Kipchak and Eastern European countries on the northern branch of the Great Silk Road.

According to Ibn al-Asir, the caravan route connecting Dashti with Kipchak, which was stopped during the march of the Mongols of Jebe and Subutai Nuyan, began to work again during the Golden Horde. In the same period, the southern branch of the Great Silk Road, connecting Central Asia with China and India, was also restored, as well as written sources and archaeological data.

In Conclusion according to Ibn Battuta, there was a great demand for Khorezm melons, which had long been exported to the world, and they were exported to India and China in dried form. At the same time as the left bank of Khorezm saw some revival, the right bank regions were still depressed. The famous traveler Ibn Battuta mentions in his memoirs that he "did not meet inhabited villages" in the distance from Urganch to Kat. At the same time, Ibn Battuta's thoughts are somewhat doubtful. All merchants and tourists who came to Khorezm noted that there were many prosperous villages and towns on the road leading to Bukhara. The results of archaeological research confirmed that most of the cities and villages destroyed during the Mongol invasion were restored at the beginning of the 15th century. It seems that the traveler Ibn Battuta thought about the fact that he did not see large and prosperous villages on the way he passed

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